

ALL-OXIDE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

Dipl.-Ing. Martin R. NEDELE
DLR Institute of Structures and Design
Pfaffenwaldring 38 - 40
D-70569 Stuttgart
Fed. Rep. of Germany

ABSTRACT

A method is presented to manufacture oxide based ceramic matrix composite materials. The method includes the use of active filler components in the matrix which consists otherwise of commercially available ceramic powders. The active filler components and their chemical reaction are investigated in more detail. They are used to counteract the shrinkage of the matrix upon sintering and therefore decrease the porosity of the composite material which does not exhibit any change in its outer dimensions upon sintering. First assessments on the quality of the composite materials are made by investigating the thermomechanical behaviour of composite samples. The behaviour of the samples subjected to external mechanical loading showed that a pseudo-plastic behaviour occurred, however the absolute strength levels are yet too low.

INTRODUCTION

Monolithic ceramic materials have superior properties compared to metals and plastics. These are corrosion and oxidation resistance, high temperature stability, high strength, high modulus and low density. Therefore, they have the potential to be used in aero-engines, stationary gas turbines and universal high temperature process technology, where high mechanical, corrosive and thermal requirements prevail. However, the major drawback of monolithic ceramic materials is their low fracture toughness. As a result, structural parts made of monolithic ceramics show hardly any damage tolerance and fail in a catastrophic manner. Monolithic ceramic materials reinforced with continuous ceramic fibres can overcome this shortcoming. The fracture toughness is increased significantly and pseudo-plasticity and damage tolerance are observed due to fibre pull-out. Nevertheless commercially available ceramic matrix composite (CMC) materials do show either significantly low oxidation resistance, due to the carbon fibres used as reinforcements, or lack long term thermal stability in the case of currently available SiC-fibres.

Latest results are presented of the ongoing work at the Institute of Structures and Design of the DLR Research Centre Stuttgart. Compared with the well-known C/C-SiC materials developed at the Institute, further efforts are undertaken to improve the long-term oxidation resistance and thermal stability of ceramic matrix composites. Whilst coating and sealing of carbon-fibre based materials does provide a short and medium term improvement, long term reliability of the coatings has to be questioned. To improve oxidation resistance, inert all-oxide composite systems seem to be advantageous and are in the process of being developed. The current research carried out in this area is presented and future directions of the development are outlined.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Based on the experience gained and lessons learned from the manufacturing of C/C-SiC via the liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) route, some important features of the LSI-process are taken into consideration when developing new manufacture methods for oxide based ceramic matrix composites. These are:

1. Classical FRP-manufacturing methods should be applicable to manufacture the green bodies.
2. Near-net shape technology should be possible to reduce final machining times and costs.
3. Envisage one-shot manufacturing technology which means that each fabrication step is carried out only once.
4. The ceramic matrix composite material has to offer significant advantages in comparison with materials in use.

Keeping these considerations in mind, the following all-oxide systems are under development. The fibres are stable oxide fibres, i.e. alumina-rich fibres. The fibres are provided by the manufacturers in preforms i.e. fabrics. The major fibre fabric used in the current investigation is a plain weave fabric called SV-500-P. The fabric is made from ALTEX fibres and it is provided free of charge for research purpose by Sumitomo Chemical Ltd., which is gratefully acknowledged. The matrix systems are alumina-rich systems too. The major component of the matrix were ceramic micron powders, i.e. commercially available alumina powders. To get a reasonable strength of the test samples in the green stage, commercially available ceramic binders, both solid and liquid are used and they account for 10% to 20% of the dry weight of the matrix. To counteract the unavoidable shrinkage of the matrix caused through drying and sintering, active filler components are included in the matrix. In the current investigation aluminium powder is used as active filler components. The amount of active filler particles in the matrix lies between 10% to 25% of the dry weight of the matrix.

The oxide powders, the active filler particles and ceramic binders are thoroughly mixed. The mixture is solved either in water or alcohol to form a pourable slurry. Due to the fine ceramic and active filler powders used, the necessary amount of solvent is rather high and lies between 25% to 30% of the dry weight of the matrix. The fibre fabrics are impregnated with the slurry and, dependent on the solid content of the slurry, a mixture of dry oxide and active filler particles is additionally sprinkled onto the impregnated fabric plies. These plies are stacked together and are uniaxially pressed in the thickness direction to form the green body. The solvent is removed by a heat treatment above the boiling point of the solvent.

The final step in the manufacture process is the high temperature thermal treatment and chemical reaction of the active filler components. The heat treatment of the material samples to be chemically densified took part at around 500° to 600° C. Afterwards the aluminium particles within the matrix are oxidised by an alkaline solution. Finally the samples are sintered to remove the crystal water arising from the chemical reaction. The alternative heat treatment is the direct sintering with simultaneous chemical reaction of the aluminium particles with the oxygen in the atmosphere to form the densified ceramic matrix composite. The final sinter temperature of all samples does not exceed 1300° C. The duration of the firing lies between 2 to 8 hours after reaching the maximum sinter temperature. The final firing takes place in two different furnaces. Both have an oxidative atmosphere however one has a forced air circulation together with a controlled atmosphere.

The typical samples are 150x70x3 mm flat plates. The thickness of 3 mm is equal to 6 plies. The calculated fibre volume fraction is in the order of 30% for all samples.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To assess the envisaged mass and density increase of the matrix systems upon sintering, pure matrix samples have been investigated using TG-DTA.

One test series has been carried out to investigate the oxidation behaviour of aluminium dependent on the sinter temperature and annealing time. Cylindrical pellets have been made from a mixture of 80% alumina and 20% aluminium by pressing the thoroughly mixed powder in a die with 1000 MPa. The following chemical reaction takes place:

None of the samples reached the theoretical weight gain of 37.8%. The maximum weight of the test series is reached by the 1300° C sample with a weight gain of 12.7%. However, the chemical reaction is incomplete for all of the samples. The shape of the weight gain curves indicate that a very long process time or high temperatures are necessary to come close to the theoretical value. Similar investigations have been carried out for a stoichiometric mixture of aluminium and silicon carbide to form mullite. The chemical reaction follows the well-known equation:

The parameter of interest is the pressure applied to form the pellets. The two samples are heat treated identically, i.e. heated with a constant gradient of 10 K/min upto 1350°C. One sample has been pressed with 500 MPa in a die whilst the other sample has not been consolidated. The results of this investigation are shown in Figure 1. The pressed sample reaches a saturation level whilst the other sample gains weight over the whole annealing time.

Figure 1: Oxidation of matrix samples

These fundamental investigations on the oxidation behaviour of the aluminium particles show that oxidation occurs without the need to alloy the aluminium with magnesium as proposed by Claussen [1]. The found result are a confirmation of Brandt [2] who showed that alloying components are not necessary for the oxidation of pure aluminium powder.

However, all test samples fall short of reaching the theoretical weight gain. A locking of the oxidation seems to be one reason. A dense surface is formed and no further oxidation occurs inside the sample because oxygen is prevented from diffusing into the core of the pellets. Additionally, the thickness of the protective oxide layer around the aluminium particles is not known. This oxide layer reduces the amount of active filler weight so that the calculated theoretical weight gain represents the upper bound.

Similar investigations on the active oxidation are carried out with composite material samples. The weight gains of the fibre reinforced test samples are even further reduced to a maximum of 4.8%. Dependent on the matrix system, the samples exhibited even mass losses upon sintering. These results occur mainly for matrix systems which contain crystal water. The crystal water can only be removed at the high sinter temperatures. A SEM picture of a composite with a matrix made from crystal water binding components is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Cross-section of a composite sample with a matrix including aluminium and calcium dioxide

The matrix consisted of alumina, aluminium and calcium dioxide together with minor amounts of silica. Some of the major problems which occur for all matrix systems during the manufacture process are clearly visible. The matrix is relatively dense between the fibre bundles. Hardly any matrix material is found within the fibre bundles. Additionally in the current matrix system the aluminium and the calcium hydroxide reacted heavily with evolution of hydrogen gas. The gaseous reaction product tends to form a porous foam. To prevent this chemical reaction the calcium dioxide is removed from the matrix added at later stage. The new test samples are heat treated and afterwards infiltrated with calcium hydroxide to react with the aluminium to form calcium aluminate upon sintering. This method gives a matrix system, as shown in Figure 3. However minor fibre degradation is already visible in this system.

Figure 3: Cross-section of a composite sample with the active filler chemically reacted

Much more severe fibre degradation is observed for a similar matrix system which is sintered at higher temperatures compared to the others. Single fibres join and form clusters within the matrix which is clearly visible in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Fibre degradation at higher temperatures

These results are an indication that the fibre-matrix systems investigated are limited to working temperatures below 1100° C.

Improved results are shown in the following two figures. Both samples are identical with respect to the fibres and matrix, however the oxidation at elevated sinter temperature is controlled for the second sample by a forced air flow. The weight gain is nearly identical,

however the second sample shows much more embedded fibres which indicates more uniform oxidation of the active filler particles.

Figure 5: Improved matrix system, standard oxidation in a furnace

Figure 6: Improved matrix system, controlled oxidation in a furnace

Whilst a change of the outer dimensions of the test samples did not occur during the sinter process, the desired reduction in porosity is not as high as expected. The porosity of the samples is measured using the Archimedes principle and the level lies between 25 to 35%.

To evaluate the quality of the samples, mechanical strength tests have been carried out. The initial results of short beam bending tests are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Short beam bending test results

The results indicate that the interlaminar debonding is the major failure mode. This failure is controlled by the density, porosity and the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding. High porosity levels seem to be responsible for the low shear strength values. However, the energy dissipating failure process shows that the envisaged toughening of the ceramic matrix material can be achieved.

CONCLUSIONS

Results have been presented on the development of all-oxide ceramic matrix composites. Emphasis has been focussed on the manufacturing process. It is based on the usage of commercially available ceramic powders, ceramic binders and active fillers. The mixture of these components is liquefied using solvents and infiltrated into the fibre fabrics to form the green body.

Fundamental investigations on the oxidation behaviour of the matrix systems have been presented together with similar results for composite materials. Increasing weight occurred for most samples, however they are smaller than the theoretical predictions.

The mechanical tests of different composite samples showed undesirably low shear strengths. However, the failure behaviour is energy dissipating and more "ductile" compared with monolithic ceramic materials.

FUTURE INVESTIGATIONS

Degradation of the fibres at elevated temperatures and too high porosity levels of the composite samples shed light on necessary future improvements to the proposed manufacture method. The investigations currently underway focus on the reduction of the porosity of the composite. The aim is to reduce the porosity level below 10%, so that the interlaminar shear strength is significantly increased. Three different possible methods are investigated i.e. to increase the fibre volume fraction, to reduce the amount of solvent and to increase the amount of active filler components.

Additionally XRD-investigations will be carried out to analyse the constituents of the matrix and to evaluate the chemical transformation of the active filler components within the composites.

REFERENCES

[1] Claussen, N., Le, T., Wu, S., "Low shrinkage reaction bonded alumina", *J. of Europ. Cer. Soc.*, 5 (1989), pp.29-35

[2] Brandt, J., Kristofferson, A., Lundberg A., "Processing of mullite based long fiber composites by slurry routes and by oxidation of Al:Si powder", *Int. Workshop Mullite 94, Irsee, Germany*